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The effect of freeze-thaw cycles on the mechanical performance of RAC

L'effetto dei cicli gelo-disgelo sulle prestazioni meccaniche di calcestruzzi con aggregati riciclati

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ABSTRACT: The recycling of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) to be used as aggregates for concrete is a potential alternative to minimize the environmental impact. In cold regions, the damage caused to concrete structures by freezing and thawing is a serious problem. This study presents the results of experimental tests aimed at investigating the influence of the use of Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCA) on concrete submitted to 150 freeze-thaw cycles. Aggregates made from laboratory-produced concrete waste were used in two size fractions (i.e., Coarse 0 - 4.8 to 9.5 mm and Coarse 1 - 9.5 to 19 mm). Concrete mixtures of normal strength and high strength were produced with only natural aggregate and mixtures with 100% RCA in each of the size fractions. The mechanical behavior and physical properties were evaluated. The results showed that, for both natural and recycled concretes, the most affected class was the normal strength class. / L'utilizzo di rifiuto da costruzione e demolizione come aggregati per la produzione di nuovo calcestruzzo rappresenta una potenziale alternativa per ridurre l'impatto ambientale del settore delle costruzioni. Inoltre, in alcune regioni, i fenomeni di degrado delle strutture in calcestruzzo dovuti alle basse temperature rappresenta una problematica seria. In questo contesto, il presente studio presenta i risultati di test sperimentali volti ad indagare l'influenza della presenza di aggregati riciclati in calcestruzzi sottoposti a cicli di gelo-disgelo. Nello specifico, gli aggregati riciclati derivano dalla demolizione di elementi in calcestruzzo prodotti in laboratorio da cui vengono generate due frazioni di aggregato riciclato: aggregato grosso tipo "0" caratterizzato da un diametro nominale da 4.8 a 9.5 mm e, aggregato grosso tipo "1" con diametro nominale da 9.5 a 19 mm. In seguito, vengono analizzate le proprietà fisiche e meccaniche di calcestruzzi di 35 MPa e 60 MPa di calcestruzzo ordinario di riferimento (contenente solo aggregato naturale) e calcestruzzi riciclati sottoposti a 150 cicli di gelo-disgelo. I risultati mostrano che, sia per i calcestruzzi ordinari che riciclati, i calcestruzzi di minore resistenza risentano di più degli effetti di degrado.

KEYWORDS: Recycled Concrete Aggregate; Recycled Aggregate Concrete; Freeze-thaw cycles; Durability; compressive strength / Aggregati riciclati da calcestruzzo; Calcestruzzo con Aggregati Riciclati; Cicli gelo-disgelo; Durabilità; Resistenza alla compressione

1 INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials in the world. Its popularity can be explained by its mechanical performance low cost and availability. In fact, several statistics show that the average annual rate of concrete production is around 1 ton per person based on the world population (Medina et al. 2014). On the other hand, every year, with demolition of buildings, millions of tons of waste are produced in the construction industry, which become a significant concern due to its impact on the conservation of natural resources and the preservation of the environment. One of the possibilities explored for the reduction of the environmental impact of concrete industry is represented by the use of recycled aggregates for the partial-to-total replacement of natural aggregates leading to the so-called Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RACs). As a matter of princi-

ple, this alternative solution not only reduces the use of natural resources, but also addresses the issue of safe and sustainable disposal of the huge volumes of construction and demolition waste generated around the world.

It is worth to mention that, due to the intrinsic characteristics of RCAs, i.e., the presence of the Attached Mortar leading to high porosity capacity of the aggregates, the resulting RAC's durability behaviour can be significantly affected (Huda & Alam 2015). In fact, the exposure to extreme temperatures, such as frost conditions, is one of the main causes of deterioration of concrete. The freeze-thaw resistance of concrete is affected by several factors, such as porosity, water content and type of aggregate (Bogas et al. 2016). Thus, before any practical applications, the freeze-thaw durability performance of RAC must be evaluated to ensure that it presents required performance even in severe exposure conditions.

Šeps *et al.* (2016) pointed out that the properties of the RACs are affected by the quality of the Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCA) that depend on the processing (crushing, grading, elimination of impurities, etc.) and properties of the original concrete. In addition, there was a considerable reduction in compressive strength after 50 freeze-thaw cycles in concrete with low cement dosage due to the deterioration of the RCA. Wu *et al.* (2017) have observed that the relative compressive strength (i.e., the ratio between the strengths measured after and before the degradation cycles) of RAC is lower than that of NAC under the same freeze-thaw cycles. By comparing the stress-strain curves after 0 and 125 freeze-thaw cycles, the descending branch of the stress-strain curve of the RAC became more pronounced, which meant that the RAC fragility increased as freeze-thaw cycles were increased. Liu *et al.* (2016) analysed the attached mortar of RCA from different origins. They concluded that there were already some initial cracks in the mortar before the beginning of freeze-thaw cycles, due to shrinkage of the concrete samples and the type of crushing used. The number of initial cracks was higher in the aggregates from low-strength concrete waste. After 150 cycles of freeze-thaw, the number of cracks in adhered mortar from high-strength concrete waste was more than five times the initial value and subsequently increased to six times the initial value, indicating that this sample suffered serious damage. However, the mortar adhered to the aggregate of low-strength concrete waste showed good resistance during the freeze-thaw cycles, with the final crack density being almost similar to the initial one.

The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of freeze-thaw cycles (performed based on ASTM C666 (2008) standard) on the physical and mechanical performance of normal (35 MPa) and high strength (60 MPa) concrete including coarse RCAs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Materials

This study concentrates the investigation on aggregates and, for this reason, a detailed characterization of their properties was carried out. The natural aggregates used were three:

- a fine fraction, composed of quartz sand, with nominal diameter smaller than 4.75 mm;
- a coarse aggregate (named “Nat-C0”), composed of coarse granite rocks, with nominal diameter between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm;
- and a coarse aggregate (named “Nat-C1”), also composed of coarse granite rocks, with a nominal diameter between 9.5 mm and 19 mm.

The Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCAs) were generated from laboratory-produced concrete waste.

The original concrete was produced with average compressive strength of 30 MPa at 28 days, a water-to-cement ratio equal to 0.6 and a cement dosage equal to 353 kg/m³. At 28 days of age, the original concrete was reduced to smaller pieces by the use of a mechanical press, and then a jaw crusher was used to further reduce particle size by crushing process. In the second step, the material was subjected to air drying and separation in an industrial mechanical sieve. The recycled material of nominal diameter between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm was classified as coarse aggregate 0, “RCA-C0”, and the material of nominal diameter between 9.5 mm and 19 mm was classified as coarse aggregate 1, “RCA-C1”. In the last step, the homogenization of the recycled aggregates was carried out through the well-known longitudinal blending bed technique, which consists of alternately and in opposite directions spreading the same amount of material along a pile. Figure 1 shows the coarse aggregates used in this study.

Figure 1. Coarse aggregates: (a) Nat-C0; (b) Nat-C1; (c) RCA-C0; (d) RCA-C1 / Aggregati grossi: (a) Nat-C0; (b) Nat-C1; (c) RCA-C0; (d) RCA-C1.

The characterization of the aggregates was performed through several tests. Specific gravity and water absorption were performed in the coarse aggregates according to NBR NM 53 (2009), and in the fine aggregate according to NBR NM 52 (2009) and NBR NM 30 (2001), respectively. Table 1 reports the results for the mentioned properties.

Table 1. Properties of the aggregates used in this study / Proprietà degli aggregati utilizzati in questo studio

Properties	Sand	Nat-C0	Nat-C1	RCA-C0	RCA-C1
D max (mm)	4.75	9.5	19	9.5	19
SG* (kg/m ³)	2447	2662	2636	2178	2105
Absorption (%)	0.5	1.5	1.3	7.3	8.2

*SG: specific gravity

A high initial strength Portland cement was used, labeled CPV-ARI according to NBR 5733 (1991), characterized by a compressive strength of 40 MPa at 28 days and a specific gravity of 3181 kg/m³. Finally, a superplasticizer (MC Powerflow 1180), with a solids content of 35% and a specific gravity of 1070 kg/m³, was used to control the workability.

2.2 Concrete mixtures composition

The mix-design of the concrete mixtures was performed according to the Compressive Packing Model (CPM) (de Larrard, 1999): the model assumes that the overall compactness achieved by the dry granular skeleton determines the properties of the resulting concrete. BetonLab Pro 3 software was used to optimize the desired properties for concrete through the CPM.

Concrete mixtures were developed for two classes of compressive strengths: normal strength of 35 MPa and high strength of 60 MPa. For each class, three mixtures were designed: a “reference” ordinary concrete with only natural aggregates (0% RCA), a recycled concrete with 100% RCA in the coarse aggregate fraction 0 and a recycled concrete with 100% RCA in the coarse aggregate fraction 1. Table 2 shows the compositions of the six concrete mixtures. The two natural mixtures were named as “CX-Nat”, where “X” indicates the strength class (35 and 60). The four RAC mixtures were named “CX-RCA-Y”, where “X” indicates the strength class (35 or 60) and “Y” indicates the fraction of coarse RCA that was used (C0 for fraction 0 and C1 for fraction 1). The superplasticizer content was 0.2% and 1.5% of solids in ratio to the cement dosage for the mixtures of 35 MPa and 60 MPa, respectively.

It is worth mentioning that in the recycled concrete mixtures, a conventional mix-design with the simple replacement of natural aggregate for RCA by volume was not performed: the CPM defines the ideal compactness for each mixture, considering the individual properties of each component material, in order to obtain the desired properties (among them, compressive strength of 35 MPa and 60 MPa at 28 days). Regarding how to consider the high absorption of the RCAs, the recycled materials were added in the dry condition to the mixture, and the absorption was considered in the calculation of the compositions by the program. The absorption value of 50% of total absorption obtained experimentally was used. This value is based on the studies developed by Pepe *et al.* (2016) and Amario *et al.* (2017). The authors concluded that the coarse RCAs absorb about 50% of the value of their total absorption during the concrete mixing process, both for fraction 0 and fraction 1.

Table 2. Concrete mixtures compositions / Composizione delle miscele in calcestruzzo

Materials (kg/m ³)	C1		C0		S	C	W
	Nat	RCA	Nat	RCA			
C35-Nat	452	0	457	0	868	325	212
C35-RCA-C0	451	0	0	373	866	338	217
C35-RCA-C1	0	361	456	0	867	336	216
C60-Nat	448	0	452	0	860	448	150
C60-RCA-C0	448	0	0	371	861	458	152
C60-RCA-C1	0	356	450	0	856	461	151

*C1: coarse aggregate fraction 1; C0: coarse aggregate fraction 0; S: sand; C: cement; W: water

2.3 Mixing procedure

Due to the high water absorption of the RCAs, a specific methodology was adopted for the mixing process: the total water was divided into two equal parts, and the addition of the parts was performed at different times of the mixture.

The mixing procedure was carried out in the following steps: 1 - all the aggregates were mixed for 1 minute; 2 - 50% of the total water was added and the mixing continued for another 1 minute; 3 - the cement was added and the constituents were mixed for another 1 minute; 4 - the superplasticizer and the second half of the water were added, and all materials were mixed for 8 minutes.

Cylindrical samples of 75 mm diameter and 150 mm height were cast from all concrete mixtures. The fresh concrete was compacted by the use of a vibrating table in two layers for 30 seconds each. Samples were demolded after 24 hours and cured at 21°C temperature and 100% humidity until the age of testing.

2.4 Test methods

The procedure to perform the durability tests on concrete subjected to freeze-thaw cycles was based on ASTM C666 (2008). The freeze-thaw cycles in the concretes were started at the age of 28 days. Initially, the specimens were kept immersed in water at 21°C temperature for 48 hours, and then the cycles were started. One cycle consisted in reducing the temperature of the specimens from 4°C to -18°C and then reheating to 4°C again. The total cycle time is 5 hours and a total of 150 cycles were performed. The cylindrical specimens were weighed in dry state, before and at the end of the procedure, to follow the mass variation. For all mixtures, non-degraded samples were kept in a moist chamber (21°C temperature and 100% humidity) as reference, and they were tested at the same age as the degraded samples for comparison purposes.

The slump tests were performed for all mixtures in accordance with NBR NM 67 (1998). The com-

pressive strength tests were performed on cylindrical samples according to NBR 5739 (2007), in Shimadzu 1000 kN mechanical press, at a rate of axial displacement of 0.1 mm/min. Compressive strength tests were performed for all mixtures for 28 days and

were also performed for reference samples (without degradation) and 150 freeze-thaw cycles samples. Tensile splitting tests were performed on all mixtures at 28 days, according to NBR 7222 (2011).

Table 3. Rheological and mechanical properties of concrete mixtures / Proprietà reologiche e meccaniche dei calcestruzzi.

Mixture	Slump mm	$f_{c,28}$ MPa	$\epsilon_{c,28}$ $\mu\epsilon$	$E_{c,28}$ GPa	$f_{t,28}$ MPa
C35-Nat	175	34.2 (\pm 2.4%)	2898 (\pm 3.2%)	21.3 (\pm 2.1%)	2.7 (\pm 1.7%)
C35-RCA-C0	180	35.7 (\pm 0.8%)	2941 (\pm 5.6%)	22.1 (\pm 2.4%)	2.7 (\pm 3.7%)
C35-RCA-C1	165	35.3 (\pm 0.9%)	2909 (\pm 3.7%)	21.2 (\pm 3.4%)	2.9 (\pm 5.2%)
C60-Nat	165	60.1 (\pm 1.5%)	2665 (\pm 1.7%)	29.1 (\pm 3.2%)	3.9 (\pm 3.2%)
C60-RCA-C0	180	60.5 (\pm 1.1%)	2602 (\pm 1.5%)	29.8 (\pm 1.5%)	4.0 (\pm 3.7%)
C60-RCA-C1	170	61.9 (\pm 1.3%)	2687 (\pm 1.8%)	30.1 (\pm 4.6%)	4.4 (\pm 3.4%)

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Properties of RAC at fresh and hardened states

Table 3 presents the mean values (and coefficient of variations) of: slump, 28-day compressive strength $f_{c,28}$, strain at maximum stress $\epsilon_{c,28}$, modulus of elasticity $E_{c,28}$ and 28-day splitting tensile strength $f_{t,28}$.

The slump results show values between 165 mm and 180 mm for all concrete mixtures, which allows a proper moldability of the concrete. Table 3 shows that all the mixtures reached values of compressive strength expected by the mix-design methodology for the age of 28 days. The results of strain at maximum stress and modulus of elasticity have very close values for the natural concrete mixtures and the RACs, in the two strength classes. Thus, it can be stated that, for both normal strength (35 MPa) and high strength (60 MPa) mixtures, the recycled aggregates do not significantly influence the stress-strain curve of the materials (Figure 2). The results of tensile strength were the similar for natural and recycled concrete for the class of 35 MPa, but for the class of 60 MPa, although similar, it can be identified that the recycled concrete with RCA-C1 showed a slightly higher tensile strength value than the others.

As for the rupture form in the compressive strength test, samples of the normal strength mixtures showed several diagonal thin fissures, maintaining their initial cylindrical appearance, while the high strength samples resulted in explosive rupture when the maximum load was reached, and the samples lost their initial cylindrical appearance. In general, all the considerations mentioned above point out that there were no significant differences in the mechanical behaviour between natural concretes and RACs: this is a consequence of the adopted mix-design methodology, which explicitly considers the specific characteristics of the RCAs and their different properties in comparison to the natural aggregates.

Figure 2. Typical stress-strain curves of 28-day compressive strength tests / Curve tensione-deformazione tipiche a 28 giorni

3.2 Mechanical performance of RAC after freeze-thaw cycles

Table 4 shows the mean values (and coefficient of variations) for reference concrete samples (without degradation, with the same age of the degradation samples) and for concrete samples subjected to the 150 freeze-thaw cycles: compressive strength f_c , strain at maximum stress ϵ_c , modulus of elasticity E_c and mass loss Δ_{ml} after degradation.

About the compressive strength of the reference samples (Table 4), the increase of time caused an increase in the values when compared to the 28 days samples (Table 3), as expected, due to hydration processes. The same was observed for the modulus of elasticity, which increased with increasing compressive strength in time, indicating a higher stiffness. Analogously, strain at maximum stress decrease when compressive strength increases. This behavior was verified for all mixtures for the two classes.

In general, freezing and thawing damage occurs on the concrete because of its porosity, as it absorbs water and then this water turns to ice at negative temperatures. This phenomenon causes reduction in the mechanical strength, alteration in the internal structure of pores and appearance of cracks in the

concrete. When comparing the results of the reference mixtures and the degraded ones (Table 4), the freeze-thaw cycles caused a decrease in the compressive strength in all the mixtures, as expected. Figure 3 shows the percentage of this decrease in compressive strength.

Figure 3. Percentage of decrease in compressive strength due to freeze-thaw cycles degradation process / Percentuali di riduzione della resistenza alla compressione dopo i cicli gelo-disgelo.

The degradation samples results are optimistic, since the recycled concretes did not necessarily present a higher drop in compressive strength than the natural concretes, which could be expected due to their greater water absorption. It is worth noting that the same behavior occurs for the two strength classes: the higher impact on the compressive strength occurred for the mixtures with the recycled coarse aggregate 0 (RCA-C0); followed by the natural concrete mixtures; and finally the mixtures that showed the lowest strength drop due to degradation processes were the ones with the recycled coarse aggregate 1 (RCA-C1). That is, the RCA with the largest nominal diameter allows a greater temperature variation (associated with a change in the volume of water when it turns into ice), causing less negative impacts on the properties of the corresponding concrete. Moreover, the results highlight that the impact on

Table 4. Mechanical properties of concrete mixtures after freeze-thaw cycles / proprietà Meccaniche dei caclestruzzi dopo i cicli gelo-disgelo

Mixture	No degradation: reference			Degradation: 150 freeze-thaw cycles			
	$f_{c,ref}$ MPa	$\epsilon_{c,ref}$ $\mu\epsilon$	$E_{c,ref}$ GPa	$f_{c,FT150}$ MPa	$\epsilon_{c,FT150}$ $\mu\epsilon$	$E_{c,FT150}$ GPa	Δ_{ml} %
C35-Nat	39.1 (\pm 3.6%)	2837 (\pm 4.2%)	23.5 (\pm 1.3%)	35.8 (\pm 0.9%)	2920 (\pm 5.1%)	22.2 (\pm 0.4%)	1,8
C35-RCA-C0	42.1 (\pm 4.3%)	2884 (\pm 4.5%)	24.1 (\pm 3.1%)	37.9 (\pm 4.1%)	2953 (\pm 4.2%)	22.3 (\pm 3.6%)	1,7
C35-RCA-C1	39.9 (\pm 2.2%)	2763 (\pm 3.5%)	23.8 (\pm 2.2%)	37.5 (\pm 1.4%)	2992 (\pm 3.0%)	22.5 (\pm 1.5%)	2,2
C60-Nat	65.0 (\pm 1.4%)	2549 (\pm 4.4%)	32.3 (\pm 2.8%)	61.2 (\pm 3.9%)	2580 (\pm 0.8%)	30.6 (\pm 3.6%)	1,2
C60-RCA-C0	64.9 (\pm 4.8%)	2516 (\pm 4.6%)	33.1 (\pm 1.5%)	60.8 (\pm 4.2%)	2681 (\pm 4.8%)	31.8 (\pm 2.8%)	1,3
C60-RCA-C1	68.0 (\pm 1.9%)	2612 (\pm 4.6%)	32.5 (\pm 3.1%)	65.7 (\pm 1.1%)	2662 (\pm 1.1%)	31.9 (\pm 1.6%)	1,5

the strength was higher for the normal strength class than for the high strength class for all the mixtures, which can be explained by the higher water absorption of concretes with lower strength due to their higher porosity.

Regarding the modulus of elasticity, the results show that the freeze-thaw cycles cause a decrease in the stiffness of the concrete for both the normal and high classes, probably due to changes in the internal pore structure due to the repeated temperature variation. Also on the modulus of elasticity, the percentages of decrease compared to the reference values were higher for the normal strength class. The results of strain at maximum stress indicate a higher deformation for the degraded concretes samples, and this behavior is associated with resistance, that is, with the drop in strength there was an increase in the strain value at the peak. Finally, the mass loss results were higher for the class of 35 MPa. In addition, it should be noted that for both classes, the mixtures that suffered the greatest mass loss were those containing RCA-C1. This fact can be related to the better capacity of the concretes produced with this material in terms of durability, as mentioned above. These results highlight that the RCA nominal diameter significantly influences on the mechanical, physical and durability properties of the RACs.

The typical stress-strain curves of concretes that suffered degradation are presented in Figure 4. In general, it is possible to observe that the typical behavior of the stress-strain curves was not affected by the freeze-thaw cycles, showing a behavior similar to the curves for 28 days (Fig. 2). The concrete samples rupture also occurred similarly to that observed for 28 days, that is, diagonal cracks in normal strength class samples and explosively for high strength class samples.

Figure 4. Typical stress-strain curves of compressive strength tests after degradation process (150 freeze-thaw cycles) / Curve tensione-deformazione tipiche dopo il processo di degrado (150 cicli gelo-disgelo)

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study reported the results of experimental tests performed on natural and recycled concrete from different compressive strength classes. The following comments can be observed:

- Mixtures of normal and high strength concrete can be performed by replacing 100% of natural coarse aggregate by RCAs in the fractions investigated in this study, provided that an appropriate methodology is adopted for the mix-design, taking into account the specific characteristics of the RCAs;

- The well-known Compressive Packing Model (CPM), originally developed for conventional structural concrete, confirms its accuracy and reliability in the case of the RAC mixtures considered in this study;

- There are no quantitatively significant variations for the recycled concrete and the corresponding natural concrete, either in terms of workability in the fresh state, nor in strength and modulus of elasticity in the hardened state at 28 days;

- Regarding the concrete performance after repeated freeze-thaw cycles, there was a decrease in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity in all mixtures. Also, all mixtures suffered mass loss at the end of the cycles;

- The impact of the degradation process on the strength and mass loss was higher for the normal strength class than for the high strength class, which can be explained by the higher water absorption of concrete with lower resistance, due to its higher porosity;

- However, the results are optimistic, since the recycled concretes produced with the RCA larger frac-

tion (RCA-C1) presented a lower percentage decrease in compressive strength than the corresponding natural concretes, clearly showing that the presence of RCA does not cause directly a decrease in the durability of the concrete;

- Coincidentally, the concrete mixtures that suffered the higher mass loss were those containing RCA-C1, and this fact can be related to the higher durability capacity of these concretes;

- These results show that the RCA diameter significantly influences the mechanical, physical and durability properties of the RACs.

Finally, although a complete replacement of natural aggregates with recycled one was not performed, it is worth mentioning that the encouraging conclusions described above are consequences of the appropriate mix-design methodology adopted for RACs and further experimental studies are required, exploring other RCAs variables to confirm the preliminary results obtained in this study.

Questo studio riporta i risultati di prove sperimentali eseguite su calcestruzzo riciclato di diverse classi di resistenza. I seguenti commenti possono essere osservati:

- Le miscele di calcestruzzo di normale e ad alta resistenza possono essere prodotte sostituendo il 100% dell'aggregato grosso naturale, a condizione che venga adottata una metodologia appropriata per il loro mix-design, tenendo conto delle caratteristiche specifiche degli aggregati di riciclo;

- Il noto Compressive Packing Model (CPM), originariamente sviluppato per calcestruzzo strutturale convenzionale, conferma la sua accuratezza e affidabilità nel caso delle miscele "RAC" considerate in questo studio;

- Non vi sono variazioni quantitativamente significative per il calcestruzzo riciclato e il calcestruzzo naturale corrispondente, sia in termini di lavorabilità allo stato fresco, né in termini di resistenza e modulo di elasticità allo stato indurito a 28 giorni;

- Per quanto riguarda le prestazioni del calcestruzzo dopo cicli ripetuti di congelamento-scongelo, si osserva una diminuzione della resistenza alla compressione e del modulo di elasticità in tutte le miscele. Inoltre, tutte le miscele subiscono delle perdite di massa a seguito dei cicli di gelo-disgelo;

- L'impatto del processo di degradazione sulla resistenza meccanica e sulla perdita di massa risulta essere più evidente per la classe normale di resistenza che per quella di alta resistenza, che può essere spiegata dal maggiore assorbimento d'acqua del calcestruzzo con minore resistenza, a causa della sua maggiore porosità;

- Tuttavia, i risultati sono ottimisti, poiché i calcestruzzi riciclati prodotti con la frazione C1 hanno presentato una riduzione percentuale inferiore della resistenza a compressione rispetto ai calcestruzzi ordinari di riferimento, mostrando chiaramente che la-

presenza di RCA non provoca direttamente una diminuzione della durabilità del calcestruzzo;

- Per coincidenza, le miscele di calcestruzzo che hanno subito la perdita di massa più elevata erano quelle contenenti RCA-C1, e questo fatto può essere correlato alla maggiore capacità di durabilità di questi calcestruzzi;

- Questi risultati mostrano che il diametro RCA influenza in modo significativo le proprietà meccaniche, fisiche e di durata dei RAC.

Infine, vale la pena ricordare che le incoraggianti conclusioni sopra descritte sono conseguenze della metodologia di mix-design appropriata adottata per i CCR e sono necessari ulteriori studi sperimentali, esplorando altre variabili RCA per confermare i risultati preliminari ottenuti in questo studio.

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